

A. D. Kosmin, V. V. Kuznetsov

Analysis of economic welfare of the population based on the purchasing power of the Russian ruble

KEYWORDS

economic welfare of the population,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The article is relevant because an adequate assessment of purchasing power allows us to better understand the state of the economy, inflation, and the population's living standards. For companies and individual entrepreneurs, knowledge of the ruble's purchasing power helps plan prices, costs, and income.

The article aims to assess the ruble's purchasing power as a tool for analyzing and forecasting economic processes.

Materials and methods. Publications in university journals, dissertations, and peer-reviewed articles on purchasing power, inflation, and economic indicators. Official statistical data: Data from the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat), the Central Bank of Russia.

Research findings. According to experts, actual inflation for 2021 in Russia exceeded 25% (and food inflation exceeded 42%). There is every reason to believe that the official inflation rate is only a part of the whole, the actual inflation rate, which is a posteriori for the mass consumer and causes intuitive doubt about its reliability, since the actual situation in the market of consumer goods and services, well, in no way corresponds to the data of 'collusive statistics'.

Conclusion. Whether the inflation rate is calculated correctly or incorrectly by the statistical agency (and the purchasing power index of Russian citizens' money is not calculated at all), it actually converts into a decrease in the real income of the population and an increase in the scale of the poor population.

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FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this study is that the correct assessment of purchasing power allows a better understanding of the state of the economy, inflation, and the population's living standards. This is important for economic decision-making at both government and business levels. In particular, government agencies use data on purchasing power to develop social programs and measures to support the population, especially during crises. For companies and individual entrepreneurs, knowledge of the ruble's purchasing power helps plan prices, costs, and revenues.

Estimating the ruble's purchasing power allows one to compare Russia's standard of living with that of other countries, which is essential for understanding global economic trends.

Thus, correctly assessing the ruble's purchasing power is essential for analyzing and forecasting economic processes.

Literature Review

A. Majumder and R. Ray write that price measurement is an important area of research in economics, since prices play a central role in welfare analysis and macroeconomic comparisons across time and space [1]. J. Hausman reviewed some aspects of the accuracy of measuring price growth and identified four sources of bias in the consumer price index [2].

According to J. Astin, consumer price index formulas have become a significant topic of discussion among economists, producers, etc., in recent years. [3]. F. Jany-Catrice published the debate's outcome which is constantly renewed whenever the consumer price index is under intense political pressure [4]. F. Jany-Catrice examines the conflicts over definitions and differences between the consumer price index, based on a set of goods and services, and the cost of living index, which is relative in individual cities [5].

Ch. Steindel writes that, despite the various alternative methods, the consumer price index, although imperfect, is still the most reliable indicator of changes in inflation [6].

K. Boudt and H. A. Luu point out that ensuring aggregate food price stability requires a forward-looking assessment of the risk that unexpected deviations in individual food inflation will lead to large shocks in aggregate food price inflation. The authors found that while meat inflation systematically has the highest weight in the aggregate index, cereal inflation was the leading risk factor for overall food price inflation from 1990 to 2018 [7].

R. Rich and Ch. Steindel review the concept of core inflation and the methods that can be used to analyze it. The authors conclude that no single measure of core inflation can be considered superior to others [8].

T. I. Iefymenko et al. write that inflation targeting increases real GDP growth. The authors developed a model of economic regulation through inflation targeting, which allows the Central Bank to determine targets for the period under consideration based on statistical indicators of the previous period [9].

H. Yilmazkuday studies the impact of inflation on the growth of per capita income in 36 developed and developing countries using structural vector autoregressive models. According to the authors, the effects of inflation on income growth in countries with stronger institutions are insignificant; it is positive in countries with weak institutions [10].

Y. Ohki et al. argue that current social indicators lack measurement frequency, making it impossible to assess people's well-being in real time. The authors suggest developing a social exclusion index using big data analysis [11].

A. Benedictow and P. Boug write that decompositions of trade price indices are usually inaccurate because the average price used as the base formula of the aggregator is not reproduced precisely. According to the authors, the ratio of geometric mean price can be accepted as a valid trade price index for homogeneous goods. In contrast, the superlative index is better suited for heterogeneous goods [12].

J. Aizenman writes that indexing wages to the price level has long been a mechanism for stabilizing real wages in case of inflation. According to the author, attention has recently shifted from indexation to broader indicators, particularly GDP deflator, nominal GNP, and others [13].

Thus, the scientific problem of correct estimation of purchasing power is the existence of different approaches to estimating purchasing power, including price indexes, consumer baskets, and other economic indicators.

Inflation is an important factor that must be considered when estimating purchasing power. However, forecasting inflation and its impact on real incomes is difficult.

Purchasing power in Russia is affected by regional differences in price and income levels and consumer preferences that may change over time, such as crises, sanctions, or changes in the world economy, which requires constant monitoring and adaptation of assessment methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In studying the topic, articles on purchasing power, inflation, and economic indicators from periodicals were used: 'Decision,' 'Journal of Economic Perspectives,' 'Current Issues in Economics and Finance,' 'Journal of Economics and Finance' and others.

Official statistical data: Data from the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat), the Central Bank of Russia.

Methods: constructing and estimating econometric models to analyze dependencies between variables affecting purchasing power.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In the Rosstat report, annual inflation in 2021 is fixed at 8.4%, including food prices that increased by 10.62% for non-food products – 8.58%; for services – 4.98% [14]. Food products remain the leaders of price growth – 39 of 43 items increased by 39, and among non-food goods and services, prices increased by 41.

It is symptomatic that the statistical office report shows higher growth indicators in the cost of several goods, but they all mysteriously [1] ‘average out’ and come to naught. Meanwhile, according to several experts, the actual inflation last year exceeded 25% (and food inflation exceeded 42%) [15].

For some reason, potatoes are not included in the list of essential food products. In Russia, potatoes are consumed at about 80 kg per capita.

The price of this root vegetable has increased two and a half times, and the price of cabbage, also absent in the Report, has risen by 125%.

According to Rosstat, building materials went up in price by 23.8% and, in fact, by two or three times more. This is especially true for metal and wood; as for clothing, footwear, and other fabrics, a minimum price increase of 2-4% is given; the actual price increase for these groups of goods is 50% or more.

According to the research center ‘ROMIR’ (the only organization that considers an alternative index of consumer prices), inflation for the entire set of goods bought by Russians amounted to 17% in 2021, more than Rosstat's estimate. and for essential foodstuffs – 35% [16].

Table 1

Growth of consumer prices per unit of products (2021) [Source: [16]]

Essential food products	Value (%)	Essential food products	Value (%)
Chicken	30.18	Vermicelli	11.31
Beef	14.07	Sugar	13.57
Pork	14.68	Cucumbers	60.50
Lamb	13.7	Tomatoes	58.82
Buckwheat	18.46	Oat Flakes ‘Hercules’	80.00
Flour	10.56	Potatoes	74.11
Egg (10 pcs.)	26.78	Cabbage	87.87

The prices for essential food products (from the tabular list) increased by 36.7% in 2021 compared to 2020.

There is every reason to believe that the official inflation rate is only a part of the whole, the actual level of inflation, which is a posteriori for the mass consumer and causes intuitive doubt about its reliability because the actual situation in the market of consumer goods and services in no way corresponds to the data of 'collusive statistics' [2].

Moreover, consumer inflation is only approximated by the average value, which is impersonal and practically has no functional significance.

Inflation should be, by definition, 'personalized' (as, for example, in the United States) according to stratification of the population: middle class, low-income, poor, and beggars. In addition, inflation has different values (far from coinciding with the statistical average) for numerous households of the above strata because each has its consumer basket (a set of goods and services), which is a function of the dominant argument – disposable income.

The consumer price index is the ratio of the current price of the consumer basket to its price in the base period (it can be a week, month, quarter, or year). In the consumer price index, the price of the most consumed product should have a greater specific weight (if a household consumes more chicken than beef, the price of chicken should have a greater weight in the consumer price index).

Underestimating the inflation rate has a 'favorable' effect on constructing the desired (rather than achieved) indicators of the population's standard of living: real monetary disposable income, minimum wages, average monthly wages, and average pensions.

Here is an example of Rosstat calculating the actual wage index in 2020 relative to its value in 2019.

The real wage index (RWI), that is, the increase or decrease relative to the previous year, is calculated as the ratio of the nominal wage index (NWI) to the consumer price index (CPI): $RWI = NWI / CPI = 107.3 / 104.9 = 1.023 = 102.3\%$ (the increase amounted to 2.3%). If the CPI is equal to 110.0%, then $RWI = 107.3 / 110.0 = 0.975 = 97.5\%$, which is a decrease of 2.5%.

Now, let's move smoothly from the consumer price index to the purchasing power index (PPI), which shows how many goods and services can be bought per currency unit. Accordingly, changes in the index indicate the dynamics of inflation in the country and the stability of the currency as a whole. The higher the price, the lower the currency's purchasing power, and vice versa.

The purchasing power index (PPI) is calculated using the following formula: $PPI = 1 / CPI$ (consumer price index).

The value of the PPI shows the relative change in the purchasing power of money in the hands of the population. If, for example, at the end of 2021, consumer inflation amounted

to 18.4%, then the $PPI = 1 / 1.184 = 0.844$. This means that the purchasing power of money has decreased on average by 15.6%; that is, for the same amount of money, the population will buy 15.6% fewer goods than in 2020 or, otherwise, maintaining the achieved standard of living in 2020 will cost 15.6% more expensive in 2021 than in 2020.

If the PPI is calculated based on real food inflation equal to 35.0%, the purchasing power of the RUR will decrease by 26.0% on average.

Now, let us touch upon the task of determining the level of indexation of household incomes in connection with rising prices. Indexation should be made far from the full extent (contrary to the statements of officials) of inflation, not on the index of consumer prices but on the index of the purchasing power of money, for some reason not taken into account by the statistical authorities. The decrease in the purchasing power of money should be indexed but not the increase in prices and inflation, and not the whole decline, because 'indexed' citizens must pay tax on the indexed amount of money – the so-called seignorage. Therefore, the level of indexation should be determined by the amount of the difference between the rate of decrease in the purchasing power of money and the storage [3]: $I_p = PPI - \text{seignorage}$.

Thus, for instance, if the percentage rate of income indexation at the end of 2021 was 18.6%, with $PPI = 26.0\%$, the seignorage (state profit) is determined as the difference between the PPI and the indexation indicator: $\text{seignorage} = 26.0\% - 18.6\% = 7.4\%$. This is the state's profit equal to the hidden losses of the country's citizens.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Solving the problem of correctly calculating the ruble's purchasing power opens up prospects in various areas of economic and social policy. Accurate measurement of purchasing power allows the government and the Central Bank to make more informed decisions on monetary and fiscal policy.

An in-depth analysis of the population's purchasing power will help design more targeted social programs to improve living standards [17], such as increasing wages, pensions, and social benefits. Accurate data on purchasing power allows businesses and households to plan their expenditures and investments more effectively.

More accurate methods for estimating purchasing power can provide a basis for future economics, sociology, and other scientific research, contributing to developing new theories and approaches. Accurate purchasing power estimates can also improve the quality of economic forecasts and models, helping predict financial trends and tendencies more accurately.

Thus, solving the problem of correctly calculating the ruble's purchasing power is of

great importance for the economy as a whole and individual citizens, businesses, and government institutions.

The general conclusion boils down to the fact that the inflation rate indicator calculated correctly or incorrectly by the statistical agency (and the index of the purchasing power of Russian citizens' money that is not calculated at all) is converted into a decrease in real incomes of the population and into the growing scale of the poor population []. This can be minimized by freezing prices for socially necessary goods. For example, in Scandinavian countries, prices for such goods are 'inviolable' until 'the end of the century'. Moreover, the growth of the poor population can be reduced by suppressing cartel conspiracies to raise prices and by making prices (non-indexed) for services of natural monopolies stationary. In addition, it is necessary to put a stop to the ongoing commercialization of the main spheres of economic development – culture, science, education, and health care, to increase public expenditures related to the performance of their social functions, namely, to concentrate in their hands the necessary and sufficient 'set' of non-commercial material objects (up to nationalization of previously privatized ones) – public halls, kiosks, academic theaters, cinemas, medical and educational institutions, pharmacies and stores, supplied by the state, with the help of the state (but all that for the wealthy consumer with a high potential for indifference to inflationary spikes).

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INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Anatoly D. Kosmin (Russia, Omsk) – Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Professor of the Department of “State, Municipal Management and Customs Affairs”. Omsk State Technical University. E-mail: kosmin.39@mail.ru

Vladimir V. Kuznetsov (Russia, Omsk) - Cand. Sci. (Tech.), Associate Professor of the Department of “State, Municipal Management and Customs Affairs”. Omsk State Technical University. E-mail: mivladirvkv@rambler.ru

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